

OGAHI TRANSLATION ACTIVITIES: THE CASE OF PERSIAN-TAJIK LITERATURE

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Abstract. The article tells about the educational and moral work considered as bright examples of world literature, the first and second translations of "Gulistan" into the Uzbek language, the article tells about the period and the literary environment in which these translations were translated, the composition, the titles of chapters of works in the translation by translators and some others. In addition, these translations contain quotations from the opinion of mature scholars.

Key words: Gulistan, Sadiy Sherozi, Ogahi, Saifi Sarai, translation.

Introduction.

Muhammadrizo Erniezbek oglu Ogahi is one of the great representatives of the literary milieu of Khorezm in the 19th century. He was born in 1809 in the village of Kiyot near Khiva (now Ogakhi collective farm). After the death of his father Erniezbek, young Ogahi was adopted by his uncle Munis. The artists who gathered around Munis had a great influence on the work of the future poet Ogahi. Ogahi received his early education from Munis Khwarizmi and later studied in Khiva madrasas. After Munis' death in 1829, Allakulikhan appointed Ogahi as his successor. From this period, Ogahi was involved in popular life and palace affairs. He retired from the post of mirab from 1857. Ogahi was widely known as a lyricist. The lyric collection "Tavziul-ashitsin" ("The Swelling of Lovers", 1872) composed by him in the last years of his life has survived to this day. Devon four hundred and seventy ghazals, three masters, eighty-nine muhammas, five musaddas, two murabbas, four musammanas, four tarje'banda, seven continents, eighty rubai, ten tuyuk, one mulamma, four chistanas, two problems, four tavnas, one bahri prayer, an answer to a lover's question, twenty stories, nineteen poems - a total of one thousand eight hundred verses. One thousand three hundred verses of Aghahi in Persian under the title Ashari Farsi are also included in Devon. This is a proof that Aghahi was also a great poet in the world of Zul-Zayn.

Main part.

In addition to poetry, Aghahi is also known as a historian and translator. He was fluent in Persian and Arabic. Treasury, in particular, is active in the field of translations. As a result of his translation work, Uzbek literature has become much richer, and readers of later times have a much richer heritage. Agahi's most effective work in this field is directly related to Persian-Tajik literature. Among these

masterpieces are Gulistan (Saadi Sherazi), Haft Paikar (Nizami Ganjavi), Kubusnoma (Unsurmaoli Kaikovus), Yusuf and Zulaikho (Abdurahman Jami), and Shah and Gado (Badridin Hilali), Badoe'ul-fi wakoedi "(, "Akhlaki Muhsini" (Huseyin Voizi Kashifi), "Bahoriston", "Salomon and Absol" (Abdurahman Jami), "Hasht-rai" (Amir Khusraw Dehlawi)[8]. As can be seen from the above, Aghahi translated masterpieces of Persian-Tajik literature. From the time of writing to the present day, these works have not lost their value, though not at all. Thanks to Agahi's translations, Uzbek readers have learnt the true value of these masterpieces. Now let us look at the direct translations. First of all, the Persian-Tajik, whose works have been translated into many languages, whose poems are still enjoyed by mankind, whose poems were written on the roof of the UN, is one of the most colourful. Representatives of Persian-Tajik literature: Sheikh Muslihiddin Saadi Sherozi, who is considered the father of ghazal property in literature, gave information about the translation of the masterpiece "Gulistan". Agahi did not translate the work in its entirety, but made a number of changes in the translation process to make it more comprehensible to the Uzbek-speaking reader. Agahi omitted twenty-five of the one hundred and eighty-seven stories in Gulistan, translated five hundred and twenty-two bytes of verse from the poem, and expressed the rest in prose. An Uzbek scholar, V. Zokhidov, commented on Ogahi's translation as follows: 'Ogahi's artistic translations require special study in the full sense of the word, with a creative essence. The poet sometimes includes his own stories and poems in the translated texts[1:256]. In the introduction to this translation, Muhammadrizo Ogahi indicates the translation of "Gulistan" as follows: "... Prince. Muhammad Rahim torah ... Ordered the poor Sheikh Saadi (may Allah have mercy on him) to translate the equestrian book "Gulistan" into Turkish. this hut. but the blessings of this world are upon him. I have tasted the juice of health and strength, and I have done my best to complete this noble service "[6:222]. Although changes have been made in the translation process, we cannot say that this work has lost its value or that the translation has become incomprehensible to Uzbek-speaking readers. On the contrary, it has been translated into a language understood by the public and conveyed to the people that this translation is still read with love and Saadi's teachings are remembered. The next translation to which we would like to draw your attention is "Haft Paikar" by Nizami Ghagjevi, another mature representative of Persian-Tajik literature who lived and worked in the 12th-12th centuries. This work is the fourth epic from Nizami Ganjavi's opera "Hamsa". Aghahi translated this work in prose, although the work was written in poetic form. As Aghahi indicates in the introduction to the translation of Gulistan, in the introduction of Haft Paikar he also indicates that the translation of this work was initiated by Prince Muhammad Rahim. The translation begins with the usual thanksgiving to Allah, the Creator of all worlds, and then to Prophet

Muhammad (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him), who is considered the ruler of the two worlds. the sultans of the world will be the obedient servants of his majesty, and that he will be worthy of the greatness of Emperor Shahanshah. He is the prophet of the end times, the greatness of his blessed being and the infinite blessings of the two worlds. But then let the wise recollections of the sages who have read this inexhaustible text should clarify: Abu Ali al-Muzaffar wa al-Mansur and Abu al-Fath Sayyid Muhammad Rahim Bahadur Khan, may God bless him and grant him peace and blessings, and may Allah bless him and grant him peace. L-Ogahi gafarallahu zunubahutakim, for seven years , maybe seventy years, he was an adherent of the throne of the state, maybe They ordered a translation and inclusion in the Turkish classification. The poor man was delighted, and I immediately became interested in the favour and began to write as much as I could. I hope that Haqq Subhanahu wa Ta'ala will fulfil this task with his karam and bring this to the King's blessed memory "[6:222]. Ogahi also translated this rare work to make it comprehensible to Uzbek-speaking readers. This is not difficult to recognise from the fact that he translated this work from verse to prose. Perhaps, when translating this work from verse to verse, it would have made the reader uncomfortable in the reading process. It is known that the process of understanding and comprehending a prose line is more convenient and easier than a poetic line. This work of Ogahi's translation is still the readers' favourite book.

The next translation is "Kubusnoma" by Unsurmaolia Kaikovus, one of the leading figures of Persian-Tajik literature of the eleventh century, dedicated to the upbringing of children. "Nightmare" has attracted the attention of Western and Eastern thinkers for centuries: in 1702-1705 it was translated into Turkish, in 1786-1787 into Uyghur by Muhammad Siddiq Rashidi, in 1881 by Kayyum Nasiri into Tatar, and in the 19th century. English, French, German and Russian have been translated into other languages. In 1935, the famous writer Saeed Nafisi, a professor at Tehran Dorylfunu, published "Nightmare in Tehran"[2:176]. The Nightmare was first translated into Uzbek by the great poet and thinker Muhammad Riza Ogahi in 1860. The manuscripts of Ogahi's translation are preserved in the Manuscript Collection of the Institute of Oriental Studies and in the Saltykov-Shchedrin Library in St Petersburg. In translating "Kubusnom" into Uzbek, the merits of Muhammad Rahimkhan Feruz, who was still a 16-year-old prince at that time, should be noted. Speaking about young Muhammad Rahim, Agahi himself is pleased to say that he was engaged in "reading, comprehending" and translated this "instruction" on behalf of the prince: "... and in his pure memory he wanted to translate it into Turkish. One day, poor Wu Muhammad Reza Agahi, I went to his meeting and presented the terms of the prayer, and I sat down in a corner of that meeting, although he had the necessary prophecy. He immediately showed me some kindness and gave me this

"instruction" and said: "Translate this copy into Turkish, so that the people of Turkish tawaf may also benefit from these teachings, and our horse, your word, will remain in the memory of time until the world crisis "[2:176]. Undoubtedly, the above-mentioned points can be said about this translation as well. This translation of Agahi is still considered a favourite among readers. This is because Agahi translated it in a simplified form so that it would be understandable during the translation process. It is known that during Agahi's translation career he also referred to the works of Yusuf Navoi and Zulaikho Mavloni Abdurahmon Jami, the teacher and friend of Alisher Navoi, who is considered the brightest representative of the 15th Persian-Tajik literature. Agahi certainly wanted to convey to Uzbek-speaking readers the differences and advantages of Jami's Yusuf and Zulaykho Mawlano over other Yusuf and Zulaykho. Jami's epic Yusuf and Zulaikho was first translated from Tajik into Uzbek by Muhammad Riza Ogahi. Ogahi fully preserved the world outlook bases of the epic, and reflected its artistic features in Uzbek with great talent and skill. The main ideological and artistic features of the work do not change and do not diminish the value of the work. On the contrary, Ogahi manages to create an Uzbek version that will never lag behind the original. Besides Agahi, this rare work was published in 1964 by Olimjon Buriev in Irfon Publishing House in Dushanbe and in 1971 by poet Nazarmat in Tashkent (an excerpt from the epic Yusuf and Zulaikha in Abdurahmon Jami's book) into Uzbek. The following is a description of Zulaikha by all three writers who translated Jami's epic: From the above passages it is clear that there is no difference between the translations in terms of meaning, but in terms of the method of narration, Ogahi's translation differs from the others. Because Ogahi did not just translate, but rather he manages to create a work that never lags behind the original by utilising all his skills. Besides, Ogahi has translated many other invaluable works. These include Alisher Navoi's contemporary Badriddin Hilali's "Shohu Darwesh" entitled "Shah and Gado" (except for the introductory part), Zainiddin Mahmudi Wasifi's "Badoe 'ul-wako", and Hussain Voizi Kashifi's "Ethics". He has also translated his works. Most of these works were published in 2020 in Tashkent. However, we cannot say the same about the copies of Maulana Abdurahman Jami's "Bahoriston" and "Salomon and Absol" and Amir Khusrawi Dehlawi's "Hasht Rai" translated by Agahi. This is because there is no clear evidence of these translations and no publication has been active.

Conclusion.

In conclusion, Muhammadrizo Erniezbek oglu Ogahi became famous for his translation works. He made a name for himself by translating invaluable works of Persian-Tajik literature, one of the richest in literature. To make the reader understand while translating, he made various abbreviations and sometimes added additions. This, at least in part, was discussed in our article.

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